

Temperature effects on geotechnical soil properties around pit thermal energy storages

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ABSTRACT: The growing global energy demand has intensified the need for renewable energy sources and efficient storage solutions. However, current district heating systems predominantly utilize oil, gas or waste combustion as primary energy sources, supplemented by electricity, and operate "on-demand" with short-term water buffer tanks. Pit Thermal Energy Storage (PTES) systems have emerged as a promising alternative for the heat supply, with water capacities of up to 1,000,000 m³. PTES typically involve excavated pits lined with protective membranes, filled with water, and covered with floating insulation to minimize heat loss, while the excavated soil is repurposed to form embankments, maintaining soil balance. Operating temperatures of 30–95°C induce thermal diffusion into surrounding soils, significantly affecting compressibility, creep, shear strength, stiffness, thermal conductivity, and moisture content. Standard geotechnical tests conducted at natural ground temperatures (10–20°C) do not capture these effects, making the study of soil thermo-mechanical behavior crucial. This research investigates compressibility and stiffness of fine-grained soils using a temperature-controlled oedometer across 20–95°C, alongside measurements of shrinkage, moisture content, and thermal conductivity. The study also proposes improved guidelines for PTES testing and monitoring to support the deployment of sustainable energy storage systems.

KEYWORDS: Pit Thermal Energy Storage, temperature-controlled oedometer, and stiffness

1 INTRODUCTION

The integration of renewable energy sources into modern and future energy systems presents both significant opportunities and technical challenges, as sources like photovoltaic (PV) solar power, wind energy, and industrial or municipal waste heat exhibit high variability in availability—both temporally and spatially. For instance, solar generation peaks in summer months, while wind generation fluctuates seasonally and meteorologically, creating mismatches between renewable energy supply and demand that require large-scale, cost-effective, and efficient energy storage solutions. To address this challenge, Large Thermal Energy Storages (LTES) have emerged as a promising approach by storing surplus renewable electricity—often through resistive heating, heat pumps, or conversion of otherwise curtailed power—and transforming it into thermal energy for later use. In many configurations, this stored thermal energy is supplied to district heating networks during periods of higher demand, displacing fossil-fuel-based heat generation and increasing the overall renewable share in the energy mix.

1.1 Principles of thermal energy storage

Thermal energy storage (TES) refers to the capture of heat energy for use later. The basic principle involves storing thermal energy in a medium whose temperature can be raised and maintained over time with minimal heat loss. For large-scale applications, the medium is typically water due to its high specific heat capacity, low cost, non-toxicity and ease of handling.

Different TES configurations have been developed for seasonal and short-term storage and reported in many previous publications (e.g., Jensen, M. 2014). Four major categories are used for large-scale applications:

- Tank Thermal Energy Storage (TTES)
- Pit Thermal Energy Storage (PTES)
- Aquifer Thermal Energy Storage (ATES)
- Borehole Thermal Energy Storage (BTES)

Each technology presents distinct thermodynamic, geotechnical, environmental and economic considerations.

The Horizon Europe-funded TREASURE project is accelerating Pit Thermal Energy Storage (PTES) deployment by connecting seven demonstration sites across Europe, leveraging operational insights from existing primarily Danish installations. The goal is to facilitate the roll-out of over 1,500 large-scale PTES units, optimizing construction, maintenance and thermal performance.

Commercial PTES systems vary in capacity from 350 m³ to 1,000,000 m³, with investment costs averaging €50/m³—larger units benefiting from significant economies of scale. Yet, current geotechnical standards rarely account for temperature effects and offer no guidance for conditions above ambient levels, despite PTES soils undergoing repeated heating cycles of up to 95 °C.

This gap prompted the TREASURE consortium to experimentally assess soil behavior under elevated temperatures and incorporate the findings into PTES system models. Understanding soil thermo-mechanical response is critical—not only for ensuring stability during construction and operation but also for long-term scenarios such as decommissioning, when a PTES is emptied. While construction practices for ambient conditions are well established, the behavior of soils subjected to repeated thermal cycling remains insufficiently understood.

The following sections explore PTES in depth—its fundamental concept, established design and construction methods, and the primary technical and operational challenges shaping its future.

1.2 Pit thermal energy storage (PTES)

Pit Thermal Energy Storage (PTES) is a large-scale (Figure 1), low-cost heat storage solution—often integrated into district heating systems—constructed by excavating a pit, typically in an inverted truncated pyramid shape, with steep, soil-stability-limited slopes sealed by impermeable polymeric liners. Excavated material is commonly reused to form perimeter embankments, sometimes reinforced or supported by retaining structures, which help minimize soil disposal, maintain mass balance, and reduce the installation footprint. A floating or fixed insulating lid limits surface heat losses, with floating modular designs preferred for large systems, while side and

bottom insulation is generally omitted due to minimal thermal losses.

Figure 1: Simplified representation of a PTES with main components labelled, thermal stratification of the water volume suggested by color

Typical PTES systems operate with charging temperatures between 30°C and 95°C and discharging temperatures down to 30°C – 40°C. The number of thermal cycles per year can vary substantially. Cycling frequency affects both the economic and thermal performance of PTES systems. Higher cycling rates can improve revenue or energy utilization but also modify the thermal gradient in surrounding soils, potentially affecting heat losses and geotechnical stability. Thermal losses occur through conduction into the ground (8–20°C) and across the lid, with groundwater further increasing losses—from 14% under static conditions to 60% in flowing water—highlighting the need to avoid high water tables or active flow zones (Sifnaios et al., 2023).

2 GEOTECHNICAL DESIGN CONSIDERATIONS FOR PIT THERMAL ENERGY STORAGE SYSTEMS

The geotechnical setting governs not only the method of excavation and structural stability but also heat loss mechanisms and maintenance requirements over the service life of the system. Unlike traditional reservoirs or waste containment facilities, PTES must accommodate sustained elevated temperatures – often approaching 90 °C - without compromising liner integrity, embankment stability, or insulation performance. This interplay between geotechnical stability and thermal performance demands a site-specific approach, informed by both soil mechanics and thermodynamic constraints.

2.1 Site conditions and excavation strategy

An open-pit excavation method, without recourse to rigid temporary support systems such as sheet pile walls, is generally preferred where soil and groundwater conditions permit. The avoidance of such retaining structures is largely economic; steel sheet piles or slurry walls introduce substantial capital costs, prolong construction schedules, and impose technical complexities. For open excavation to be viable, the in-situ soils must exhibit sufficient stability at steep temporary slopes and be amenable to removal using conventional earthmoving equipment. Cohesive soils of moderate plasticity—such as well-graded sandy clays—offer advantages in excavation stability, while clays of high plasticity, normal-consolidated clays and some sands may require additional stability measures to ensure slope stability (flattened slopes).

The soil's particle size distribution, plasticity index, and natural moisture content govern both excavation ease and embankment performance. Heterogeneous strata containing cobbles, boulders, or cemented horizons can significantly increase excavation costs and may necessitate specialized mechanical or blasting techniques, reducing the economic advantage of PTES over alternative storage concepts.

2.2 Groundwater considerations

Groundwater control is a principal geotechnical challenge in PTES construction. Ideally, the phreatic surface should be located well below the base of the excavation, eliminating the

need for temporary and/or continuous dewatering. A shallow water table increases construction risk by inducing slope instability, piping, or hydraulic base heave during excavation, and later by enhancing thermal losses through adventive transport of heat in flowing groundwater. From a hydrogeological standpoint, low hydraulic conductivity in surrounding soils is advantageous, as it suppresses lateral groundwater movement beneath the storage volume.

When elevated groundwater levels are unavoidable, site-specific assessments must determine whether natural groundwater flows could create an unacceptable thermal loss. In such cases, engineered barriers—such as low-permeability cutoff walls—may be implemented to control seepage and prevent thermal dispersion. The thermal conductivity of the surrounding soils, strongly influenced by their degree of saturation, also plays a role; dry soils offer superior insulation compared to moist or saturated soils, reducing conductive heat transfer away from the pit.

2.3 Geometry and slope stability

From a purely thermodynamic perspective, a spherical pit shape would minimize heat losses by achieving the lowest possible surface area-to-volume ratio. However, geotechnical and constructability constraints make such forms impractical. The most common configuration in large PTES facilities is an upturned frustum of a pyramid or cone (Figure 2). This geometry accommodates stable slopes for excavation, provides a broad base for the liner, and facilitates straightforward placement of the top insulation in rectangular plane shapes.

Steeper slope angles offer several advantages, including a reduced plan area for the top insulation—one of the system's most costly components—leading to lower capital costs, decreased thermal losses, and improved thermal stratification. However, the maximum feasible slope angle is constrained by geotechnical factors such as the soil's internal friction angle, cohesion, and pore pressure conditions. For instance, granular soils may allow slope angles of 30°–35° under dry conditions, while cohesive clays can sustain steeper slopes of up to 45°, depending on their over-consolidation ratio (OCR), weathering, and moisture content. In contrast, high-plasticity clays with a lower internal friction angle may significantly restrict the permissible slope angle. To ensure structural integrity, stability analyses must be conducted to verify that the chosen slope design meets the required safety factors under both construction and operational loads. Additionally, long-term considerations, including decommissioning scenarios, must be accounted for in the design process.

Figure 2: Marstal PTES: excavation-nearing completion with membrane installation in progress. The central structure is a 16-meter-

tall water inlet and outlet tower, integral to the operational phase of the Pit Thermal Energy Storage system.

2.4 *Time-dependent stability in cohesive soils*

In PTES construction on cohesive soil deposits, particularly marine clays and other fine-grained strata, slope stability must be evaluated with careful consideration of time-dependent changes in shear strength. Short-term excavation stability in such soils is often governed by undrained shear strength, which can permit relatively steep side slopes immediately after excavation. Under undrained conditions, excess pore water pressures generated during excavation have not yet dissipated, and the soil mass temporarily retains higher shear resistance. Ideally, rapid excavation and immediate loading—such as filling with water—might be a viable short-term strategy, but for a larger PTES this is not possible in practice due to the time-consuming soil works, liner works and water-filling (takes more than a year to complete).

The transition from undrained to drained conditions over time can significantly alter stability outcomes. Once pore pressures dissipate, effective stresses govern shear strength, and in many cohesive soils, the drained shear strength is substantially lower than the undrained value. Stability analyses based on long-term drained parameters often predict shallower stable slope angles, and when appropriate safety factors—such as those required by Eurocode 7—are applied, slopes acceptable under undrained assumptions may become unstable. From a design safety perspective, slope designs will often be based on drained strength parameters.

2.5 *Liner and insulation interface with geotechnical works*

The geotechnical design must integrate with the thermal containment system, particularly the liner and insulation layers. The base is typically sealed with a 2.5 mm HDPE geomembrane, which requires a smooth, stable subgrade to prevent puncture or stress concentrations. Any differential settlement in the subgrade could compromise liner integrity over time, especially under elevated temperatures. This necessitates careful compaction control during subgrade preparation and ongoing monitoring during operation. Furthermore, sharp grains (gravels) in the surface shall be avoided due to a risk of a puncture of the membrane.

The top insulation layer, while primarily a thermal consideration, may also interact with geotechnical aspects through load transfer onto embankments or backfill layers. Usually, insulation consists of light materials with delimited impact on geotechnical matters, but potential settlements in built-up embankments shall not compromise the planned water level in the PTES and the thermal barrier.

2.6 *Embankment formation and soil reuse*

A common strategy to improve project sustainability and economics is to reuse excavated soil in the construction of embankments around the pit. Achieving a balanced earthwork—where excavation volumes match fill requirements—eliminates the costs and environmental impacts associated with soil disposal and importation.

From a geotechnical perspective, the suitability of excavated material for embankment construction depends on its compaction characteristics, including moisture content and absence of deleterious materials such as organics or oversized particles.

Compaction should be carried out in controlled layers, with field density testing to verify compliance with design specifications, typically expressed as a percentage of maximum dry density obtained from laboratory Proctor tests. Properly

constructed embankments contribute to slope stability and may serve as platforms for inspection and maintenance activities.

Effects on soil due to possible dry-out of the soil – especially in the embankments above ground level – must also be considered.

2.7 *Integrated thermal-geotechnical design and Monitoring consideration*

For PTES systems to achieve long-term structural integrity and operational efficiency, geotechnical design must explicitly account for the influence of elevated temperatures on soil behavior. This requires incorporating temperature-dependent soil properties — such as volumetric strain, stiffness, creep rates, permeability, and shear strength — into slope stability analyses, settlement predictions, and liner support assessments. These parameters should not be extrapolated from conventional ambient-temperature tests; instead, laboratory investigations must be performed under realistic operating temperatures (30–95 °C) and stress paths representative of in-situ loading during both construction and operation.

Design models should integrate these thermo-mechanical datasets into finite elements or limit equilibrium analyses, enabling accurate prediction of deformation patterns and stability margins over the full thermal cycling range. Special attention should be paid to the first years of operation, when thermal consolidation, secondary compression, and pore pressure redistribution can be most pronounced.

Complementing the design stage, a robust monitoring program is essential during initial operations. It should automatically track critical parameters like settlement, pore pressure, and temperature. This real-time data allows for the early detection of performance deviations, enabling proactive interventions—such as adjusting thermal cycles or water levels—to prevent instability, liner damage, or efficiency loss.

A special focus point is establishment of a warning system in case of leakage from the PTES (damaged liner), which could jeopardize the stability of the embankments. A drainage system below the liner is often introduced to avoid accumulation of water below the liner during installation and built-up of unacceptable pore water pressures in the embankments.

3 LITERATURE ON THERMAL BEHAVIOR OF SOIL

The geotechnical design considerations for PTES underscore that its long-term performance is inextricably linked to soil behavior under sustained elevated temperatures. Conventional geotechnical practice, based on ambient-temperature soil mechanics, provides inadequate guidance for these conditions, as thermal energy profoundly alters the properties of fine-grained soils. As comprehensively reviewed by Casarella et al. (2021), heating induces significant changes in shear strength, permeability, pore water pressure, and creep behavior, driven by volumetric changes and microstructural evolution under thermo-mechanical loading. This established body of literature forms the critical foundation for understanding and predicting the soil response that governs PTES stability and efficiency.

3.1 *Thermally induced volume change behavior of saturated soil under drained conditions*

Under drained conditions, the volumetric response of saturated soils to temperature changes is primarily governed by their overconsolidation ratio (OCR). A key finding is the existence of a transition temperature, where soil behavior shifts from expansion to contraction upon heating (Baldi et al., 1988). While this transition temperature generally increases with OCR (Hoseinimighani & Szendefy, 2022), its dependency remains a

point of disagreement in the literature (Laloui & Cekerevac, 2003).

The consolidation state dictates the fundamental response:

- Normally consolidated (NC) soils (low OCR) typically undergo irreversible volumetric change (thermal contraction) and independent of the applied stress (Abuel-Naga et al., 2007; Sultan et al., 2002).
- Heavily overconsolidated (OC) soils (high OCR) exhibit reversible, elastic expansion upon heating, up to a critical point (Sultan et al., 2002; Abuel-Naga et al., 2007).

This behavior stems from microstructural changes: heating weakens inter-particle bonds. In NC soils, this leads to a collapse of the vulnerable structure, causing permanent contraction. The more robust fabric of OC soils allows for reversible, elastic expansion until a critical thermal stress is exceeded (Baldi et al., 1988). During thermal cycles, heating generally causes expansion and cooling causes contraction, but the net volumetric change is governed by the soil's consolidation history (Coccia & McCartney, 2012).

3.2 *Thermo-mechanical behavior of saturated soils under undrained conditions*

Under undrained conditions, heating consistently increases pore water pressure in saturated fine-grained soils, though this effect is less pronounced in soils with higher overconsolidation ratios (OCR) (Abuel-Naga et al., 2007). The specific response is governed by the OCR:

Normally Consolidated (NC) soils exhibit a strong, reversible increase in pore pressure. This is due to the thermal expansion of pore fluid and a decrease in the shear resistance of adsorbed water, which together reduce the effective stress. This mechanism explains the reversible nature of the pore pressure response in NC soils upon cooling (Abuel-Naga et al., 2007; Ghaaowd et al., 2015).

Overconsolidated (OC) soils show a more muted and often irreversible pore pressure response, sometimes involving negative pressures. This is attributed to thermally induced particle rearrangement that permanently alters the soil fabric.

Consequently, undrained heating poses a greater risk of instability for NC soils due to the significant, reversible loss of effective stress.

3.3 *Volumetric change under thermal cycles*

Cyclic thermal loading causes distinct volumetric responses in saturated fine-grained soils based on their consolidation state. Normally consolidated (NC) soils exhibit thermo-elasto-plastic behavior, undergoing irreversible contraction over the initial ~10 cycles before stabilizing to a reversible pattern of thermal expansion and cooling contraction. This accumulation of plastic strain, known as thermal secondary compression, results from particle rearrangement and structural collapse, with greater compression in higher clay-content soils (Bai & Shi, 2017). Eventually, a stable soil fabric forms, ceasing further irreversible deformation.

Conversely, over-consolidated (OC) soils demonstrate predominantly thermo-elastic behavior, characterized by reversible expansion and contraction with minimal irreversible volume change throughout cycling (Di Donna & Laloui, 2015). Consequently, NC soils experience progressive stabilization through thermal cycles, while OC soils maintain elastic resilience.

3.4 *Thermal hardening*

Sequential thermo-mechanical loading can induce thermal hardening, a phenomenon where temperature cycles reduce soil compressibility and increase stiffness (Shetty et al., 2019). This is evidenced by a change in the slope of the volumetric strain

versus effective stress curve, indicating a stiffer soil response after thermal cycling (Shetty et al., 2019; Cui et al., 2000).

The hardening effect manifests as a cumulative decrease in volumetric strain under constant effective stress (Ma et al., 2017). Crucially, thermal cycling at a given stress level does not influence the volumetric response to subsequent cycles at higher stresses, suggesting the hardening effect is locked in at the pre-consolidated state (Shetty et al., 2019).

3.5 *Thermal dependent creep behavior*

Elevated temperatures significantly accelerate creep deformation in soft clays, with both creep rate and creep index increasing during thermal loading (Jarad et al., 2019). This thermal enhancement is particularly pronounced in low-density clays, which exhibit higher creep indices under heated conditions.

The mechanism involves thermal reduction of interparticle bond strength and decreased pore water viscosity, facilitating particle rearrangement and irreversible strain accumulation (Jarad et al., 2019; Li et al., 2018). These microstructural changes enable greater deformation under sustained loading, making temperature a critical factor in long-term clay stability.

3.6 *Shear strength parameters*

Research on thermal effects on soil shear strength reveals contradictory findings, with studies reporting increased (Maghsoodi et al., 2020), decreased (Ghahremannejad, 2003), or negligible changes (Burghignoli et al., 2000; Yavari et al., 2016). This variability stems from differing soil responses to thermal loading. Normally consolidated soils typically show strength increase due to thermal hardening from particle rearrangement and contraction during drained heating (Abuel-Naga et al., 2007b; Kuntiwattanakul et al., 1995).

The response mechanism differs significantly between soil states. In over-consolidated soils, strength changes depend on competing mechanisms: strengthening through enhanced interparticle contacts versus weakening through facilitated particle sliding along shear planes (Kuntiwattanakul et al., 1995). The balance between these micro- and macro-resistance mechanisms determines the net strength variation.

At the parameter level, the friction angle demonstrates minimal temperature sensitivity, while cohesion shows inconsistent trends across different soils (Maghsoodi et al., 2020). These contradictions highlight the complex interplay of mineralogy, stress history, and loading conditions, indicating need for further systematic investigation of temperature-dependent shear strength behavior.

4 LABORATORY TESTING

While existing research establishes temperature as a critical factor in soil behavior, this knowledge derives primarily from fundamental studies under controlled conditions. Translating these findings into practical engineering parameters for PTES design requires laboratory investigations that replicate actual operational environments. This section presents a testing methodology that modifies conventional geotechnical testing procedures to directly characterize soil properties under the thermal cycling (20–95°C) encountered in PTES systems.

4.1 *Standard procedure for laboratory investigation of soils for PTES applications*

Current standard tests, like those in Eurocode 7, are conducted at ambient temperatures and fail to capture the thermo-mechanical soil behavior critical to PTES. To address this, we propose an enhanced framework that modifies conventional procedures to explicitly quantify temperature-dependent

properties. It systematically evaluates four key aspects: physical characterization, thermal properties, hydraulic properties, and mechanical behavior under thermal loading. The required testing encompasses:

1. Physical characterization (index properties, particle size distribution, shrinkage limits).
2. Thermal properties (conductivity via needle probe across varying saturation states).
3. Hydraulic properties (permeability and soil-water retention curves).
4. Mechanical behavior under thermal loading using modified oedometer and triaxial apparatus.

Specifically, temperature-controlled oedometer tests should determine compression indices (C_c , C_r) across operational temperatures (20-90°C) and under thermal cycling conditions. Advanced triaxial testing under temperature-controlled consolidated-undrained conditions provides crucial data on temperature-dependent shear strength parameters (c' , ϕ') and pore pressure response.

4.2 Soil laboratory testing in the TREASURE project

Within the TREASURE project framework, this study addresses critical knowledge gaps in soil behavior under cyclic thermal loading through experimental characterization of thermo-hydro-mechanical (THM) properties. Soil samples were obtained from Hjørring, Denmark, representing a potential PTES construction site characterized by calcareous, sandy silty clay of medium plasticity - a late glacial marine deposit with slight overconsolidation.

4.2.1 Modified oedometer apparatus for thermal testing

A specialized oedometer apparatus was developed to investigate soil response across the operational temperature range of PTES systems (20-90°C). The modified system maintains fundamental oedometer principles while incorporating critical thermal control capabilities (Figure 3):

- Loading system: High-precision external LVDT (resolution ± 0.1 mm).
- Instrumented cell: Fixed-ring design with ultrasonic transducer compatibility.
- Thermal control and insulation system: Custom heating jacket with multi-zone thermal isolation.

Figure 3: Photo of the setup for incremental loading tests, with thermal application around the temperature-controlled sample volume: (a) Temperature controlled incremental loading test setup in full (b) the oedometer cell including the load frame, insulation and the LVDT

4.2.2 Experimental methodology and initial findings

Two incremental loading tests were conducted on soil samples retrieved from Hjørring (Denmark), where establishment of a PTES is considered with a depth of approximately 12 m, corresponding to typical PTES bottom depths in practice. A

number of boreholes were made in different areas of interest to find the optimal location for the PTES. The soil (Table.1) was mostly classified as calcareous, sandy, silty clay of medium plasticity, a late glacial marine deposit, which is slightly overconsolidated.

Table 1. Soil physical properties.

Parameter	Symbol	Value	Unit
Water content	w	25	%
Liquid limit	LL	47.7	%
Plastic limit	PL	21.3	%
Plasticity index	PI	26.4	%
Linear shrinkage	LS	11	%
Permeability	k	2.5E-11	m/s
Thermal conductivity	λ	Sat. (2.0-2.5) Dry (0.2-0.4)	W/m.K

The first oedometer test served as a reference to assess soil behavior without thermal influence, while the second test was performed to evaluate volumetric strain differences between heated and unheated conditions:

- Test 1: the unheated specimen was loaded incrementally up to 4800 kPa (the equipment's maximum capacity).
- Test 2: the heated specimen was loaded to 150 kPa (the maximum capacity for the thermal test setup).

The heated test was conducted in compliance with DS/EN ISO 17892-5; however, since the standard does not account for heating and drying, the procedure was adapted accordingly. An intact specimen with dimensions of 20 mm in height and 37.7 mm in diameter was used. Initially, the specimen was restored to its in-situ stress state. Subsequently, the samples were heated to temperatures up to 90°C under constant load, inducing drying and subsequent shrinkage. Once no further shrinkage was observed, the temperature was reduced, and the specimens were removed from the oedometer cell, after which they were measured and weighed. Finally, the samples were oven-dried, followed by post-drying measurements and weighing to assess shrinkage and moisture loss.

Figure 4 presents a comparison of the compression behavior observed in standard unheated tests and thermally controlled incremental loading tests. The results show that heating under a vertical effective stress of 150 kPa caused a marked increase in axial strain, rising from 3.8% to 8.6%. This increase is attributed to the combined effects of thermal softening followed by stiffening due to drying. The observed axial strain increase under thermal loading confirms that conventional analysis would significantly underestimate deformations, with direct implications for system design and stability. Synthesizing these findings with the earlier reviewed literature and design considerations leads to the following conclusions and perspectives for future work.

Figure 4: Effect of temperature on axial strain with effective vertical stress

Figure 5 illustrates the axial strain evolution during temperature application at the final loading stage (150 kPa) in Test 2, where a constant temperature of 87°C was maintained throughout the heating phase to evaluate the thermal effects on soil deformation.

Figure 5: Application of temperature and its effect on the axial strain for test 2

5 CONCLUSIONS

The paper reviewed literature on soil properties at elevated temperatures, focusing on thermo-mechanical behavior and volume changes under both drained and undrained conditions. It emphasized that thermo-mechanical responses are strongly influenced by soil type, mineralogy, and overconsolidation, with thermal hardening, creep, and shear strength changes being particularly relevant for PTES implementation.

In addition, the paper examined geotechnical design considerations for PTES systems, addressing slope stability, liner performance, and the influence of cyclic heating on soil-structure interaction—factors critical for ensuring long-term operational safety and efficiency.

Furthermore, initial experimental results demonstrate significant thermo-mechanical coupling (THM), where elevated temperature under moderate vertical stress substantially increased axial strain. This response reflects complex coupled mechanisms including initial thermal softening followed by drying-induced stiffening, highlighting the inadequacy of conventional geotechnical parameters for predicting PTES performance.

Critical knowledge gaps persist in understanding long-term drained behavior, time-dependent responses to cyclic thermal loading, and coupled THM effects during operational scenarios. Future research will include additional experimental studies to systematically characterize these effects across different soil types and stress paths.

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